

Sample Population and Data Sources Details

1. Overview of the Nigerian fintech holding company

S/No.	Company Aspect	Description
1.	Company type	Fintech holding company with five divisions (operating companies)
2.	Year established	2008
3.	Industry	Financial and banking services, technology
4.	Organisational structure	Hierarchical and divisional organisational structure with middle management
5.	Geographical distribution	Multiple countries with headquarters located in Nigeria
6.	Global workforce	142
7.	Years using agile methods for software development	Eight
8.	Project studied	Agile software development project involving bespoke development of a solution to be used by financial services providers for their customers' inter-banking services
9.	Project status at the time of data collection	Ongoing
10.	Project duration	Two and a half years
11.	Agile methods used for the project	Scrum, Dynamic System Development Method (DSDM), and Kanban

2. Organisational structure of case organisation

3. Case study data sources (position: senior management (SM), middle management (MM), lower-level workforce (LOW))

Data Source	Details					
	Participants	Job Title	Level/ Team	Duration of IT Experience	Duration of Agile Methods Experience	Interview Duration
Nine semi-structured interviews (eight face-to-face interviews and one virtual interview using GoToMeeting online meeting software), audio recordings, virtual interview recording, and transcripts	P1	Head of Operations, alias Acting Chief Operating Officer of TECHCOY division, and Solution Delivery Manager	MM. Member of agile team delivering project (solution delivery)	4.5 years	2 years	2 hours 33 minutes
	P2	App Support Team Member (Software Engineer)	LOW. Member of agile team delivering project (development)	2 years	1 year	48 minutes
	P3	Product Enhancement Team Member (Software Engineer)	LOW. Member of agile team delivering project (development)	3 years	8 months	57 minutes
	P4	Group Chief Information Officer of HOLDCOY	SM	15 years	11-12 years	1 hour
	P5	Project Manager and Business Analyst	LOW. Member of agile team delivering project (solution delivery)	3 years	3 years	1 hour 12 minutes
	P6	Head of Technology and Scrum Master, alias Acting Chief Technical Officer of TECHCOY division, Technical Lead, and Technical Director	MM. Member of agile team delivering project (development)	17 years	6 years	1 hour 6 minutes
	P7	Head of Business Development, alias Acting Chief Commercial Officer of TECHCOY division	MM. Member of agile team delivering project (business development)	2 years	1 year	59 minutes
	P8	Operational Excellence Manager	MM. Member of an internal shared services team that interfaces with the agile team delivering project (operational excellence)	10 years	5 years	1 hour 27 minutes
	P9	TECHCOY CEO (divisional CEO)	SM. Member of agile team delivering project	14 years	6-8 years	1 hour 25 minutes
Meeting observations and notes	Observation of three TECHCOY agile team meetings, viz., daily Scrum meeting (30 minutes), weekly sprint planning meeting (3 hours), and monthly performance review (MPR) executive session (4 hours 40 minutes). The TECHCOY agile team was co-located and based at HOLDCOY's headquarters in Nigeria.					
Company document	Organisational structure document.					
Emails and instant messaging	Follow-up email and instant messaging correspondence with participants to clarify and validate collected research data.					
Company profile and project profile questionnaires	Two completed company profile and project profile questionnaires were filled by the Head of Operations (Participant 1, MM) and HOLDCOY's Head of Human Resources (Participant 10, SM) respectively. The Head of Human Resources was not considered an agile practitioner in this study, therefore his profile details are not included. However, he provided useful company profile information. The questionnaires are not for quantitative analysis. They were used to facilitate collection of data for describing the case organisation and project.					